

Modulation of the proton transfer dynamics of a 3-hydroxychromone dye in nonionic micelles : The role of the hydrophile-lipophile balance parameter

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Abstract : The photophysics of 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxychromone (FHC) was explored in three different non-ionic micelles of Triton X-100, Brij-58 and Tween-20. FHC exhibits a dual emission, attributable to the excited normal (N*) and tautomer (T*) forms resulting from an excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) reaction (N*→T*). The ESIPT dynamics of FHC in the non-ionic micelles demonstrates a dependence on the hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) parameter of the surfactants by an increase in the kinetic constant of ESIPT reaction (k_{PT}) with a decrease in HLB. A comparison of the difference in positions of the N* and T* band maxima, ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$), between the micelles and polar protic solvents indicates to location of the dye in the polar palisade layer of the non-ionic micelles, which were further corroborated from the time-resolved anisotropy measurements. The slowest ESIPT dynamics in Tween-20 among the three non-ionic micelles is attributed to its relatively stronger hydration than others, and originates from its highest HLB value of 16.7, whereas a weaker hydration owing to a lower HLB value of 13.5 leads to the fastest proton-transfer dynamics in Triton X-100. However, in addition to the lower HLB value of its constituent surfactants, weaker hydration of the Triton X-100 micelles than the other two may originate from a weaker micelle-water interaction due to its more rigid environment.

Keywords : ESIPT, HLB parameter, band maxima.

Introduction

The issue of unraveling the structure, dynamics and reactivity in complex biological systems has been a long standing goal for the chemists and biologists. Self-organized molecular assemblies like micelles and vesicles, closely mimic most of the natural and biological systems¹⁻³. As a consequence, study of such organized assemblies, especially the micelles, constitutes an emerging frontier of contemporary research because of their implications in biology, catalysis, and advanced materials. The hydrophobic core, and the polar hydrophilic shell of a micelle which is often termed as 'Stern layer' for the ionic and 'palisade layer' (Scheme 1) for the non-ionic micelles, render it to act as a nanoreactor, which may drastically modulate the reactivity of an entrapped solute due to its location with respect to the micelle-water interface⁴.

Although, the reactivity and dynamics of photoinduced intermolecular and intramolecular proton transfer reactions in micelles has been addressed by a few groups⁵⁻⁸ the aspect of monitoring the dependence of the reaction dynamics of an excited state intramolecular proton trans-

fer (ESIPT) process on the hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) of different classes of non-ionic micelles is yet to be explored. This is an interesting topic of worth addressing, since (i) the micelle-water interface is the preferred site of solubilization, even for hydrophobic molecules⁹ and (ii) the hydration of the palisade layer are likely to be different for different types of non-ionic micelles owing to a difference in their hydrophile-lipophile balance and molecular architecture. The hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) is one of the fundamental characteristic of non-ionic surfactants and is *defined as twenty times the ratio of the molecular mass of the hydrophilic portion of the molecule to the molecular mass of the whole molecule*¹⁰ and depends on their molecular structure and type¹¹. The HLB value is measured on a scale of 0 to 20, where higher numbers correspond to the stronger hydrophilicity and greater water solubility of the non-ionic surfactants^{11,12}.

In this context, we explored the photophysics of a fluorescent dye 2-(2-furyl)-3-hydroxychromone (FHC, Scheme 1) in three different non-ionic micelles of Triton X-100, Brij-58 and Tween-20 with distinctly different HLB

Scheme 1. (a) 2-(2'-Furyl)-3-hydroxychromone (FHC), (b) cross-section of a non-ionic micelle and (c) non-ionic micelles of different types.

values of 13.5, 15.7 and 16.7, respectively. FHC is a potential probe for monitoring the ESIPT dynamics in the palisade layer of these non-ionic micelles, because (i) it exhibits dual emission bands, ascribed to the excited normal (N^*) and tautomer (T^*) forms, resulting from an ESIPT ($N^* \rightarrow T^*$) reaction¹³ (Scheme 2), (ii) the dual emission bands of FHC is sensitive to the environment due to a modulation of the ESIPT dynamics¹³, (iii) the palisade layer (Scheme 1) of the micelle-water interface is most likely the preferred site for localization of the FHC dye in non-ionic micelles, as it is highly polar and possesses hydrophilic 4-carbonyl and 3-hydroxy moieties and (iv) the dye possesses a furan ring which increases the partial negative charge on the 4-carbonyl oxygen¹⁴ through a possible conjugation with the chromone ring and thus favors a strong intermolecular H-bonding interaction with water as well as other protic solvents¹³.

Herein, we present results of steady state as well as

Scheme 2. (A) Excited state intramolecular proton transfer of 2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxychromone; for irreversible ESIPT reaction, $k_{PT} \gg k_{-PT}$ where k_{PT} is the rate constant of the ESIPT reaction; N , T and N^* , T^* are the normal and proton-transferred tautomer forms in the ground and excited states, respectively; λ_{N^*} and λ_{T^*} are the short and long-wavelength emission bands, respectively. (B) Two possible resonance structures of the N^* form, showing the electronic involvement of the 2-furyl group.

time-resolved intensity and anisotropy measurements, unambiguously demonstrating the occurrence of an excited-state intramolecular proton-transfer reaction on a distinctly different time-scale in the non-ionic micelles, which enables us to assess the role of hydrophile-lipophile balance and molecular architecture of the surfactant headgroups in modulation of the ESIPT dynamics.

Experimental

2-(2'-Furyl)-3-hydroxychromone (FHC) was synthesized as previously described^{13,15}. The surfactants Brij-58, Tween-20 and Triton X-100 were procured from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. The stock solutions of the surfactants were prepared in deionized water (from Millipore Milli-Q nanopure water system) at the concentration range of 80 to 160 mM in order to maintain the micelle concentration in the range of 0.7 to 3.0 mM. A small quantity (2 μL) of the FHC stock solution in methanol (3.5 mM) was transferred to the micellar solution to yield a solution with a FHC concentration of 7 μM , used for the measurements of UV-Vis, steady state and time-resolved fluorescence decays. The total methanol content of all the final solutions of FHC in micelles were kept at

<0.1%. To guarantee a low probability of having two or more chromophores occupy a single micelle, the micelle concentration $[M]$, was kept 100 times higher than the chromophore concentration (7 μM). For a Poissonian distribution of the probe, this ensures that less than 2% of the occupied micelles contain two or more FHC molecules, which effectively prevents an electronic excitation transfer among the fluorophores. The micelle concentration was determined from the surfactant concentration $[S]$, the aggregation number, N_{agg} , and the critical micelle concentration, cmc, as follows

$$[M] = ([S] - \text{cmc})/N_{\text{agg}} \quad (1)$$

The solutions were then allowed to equilibrate for one hour in the dark prior to the steady state and time-resolved measurements. The binding constants (K_d) between the dye and the micelles were determined from measurements of the fluorescence intensity of the short- and long-wavelength emission bands (I_{N^*} , I_{T^*}) using the following relation¹⁶

$$(F_{\text{max}} - F_0)/(F_t - F_0) = 1 + K_d/[M] \quad (2)$$

where $F_{\text{max}} = (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*})$ ratio under conditions of complete micellization, $F_0 = (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*})$ ratio in absence of surfactant, and $F_t = (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*})$ ratio in micellar solutions at a micelle concentration $[M]$.

The solutions were then allowed to equilibrate for one hour in the dark prior to the steady-state and time-resolved measurements. Quantum yields (Φ , Φ_{N^*} and Φ_{T^*}) of the dye were determined with respect to a solution of 3-hydroxyflavone in toluene as a reference ($\Phi = 0.29$)¹⁷. The quantum yield was calculated based on the following equation :

$$\Phi_S = \Phi_R \cdot (I_S A_R / I_R A_S) \cdot (n_S / n_R)^2 \quad (3)$$

where the subscripts S and R refer to the sample and reference compound, respectively. I is the integrated area under the corrected emission spectrum. A is the absorbance of the solution at the excitation wavelength ($A < 0.05$) and $(n_S/n_R)^2$ is the correction for the refractive index. For the determination of fluorescence quantum yield (Φ_{N^*} , Φ_{T^*}) of each of the two emission bands, separately, the fluorescence spectra were decomposed into two separate bands using an iterative non-linear least-squares method based on the Fletcher-Powell algorithm¹⁸. The shape of the individual short and long-wavelength emission bands was approximated by lognormal function¹⁹,

which accounts for the asymmetry of the spectral bands. All of the spectroscopic measurements were performed at 25 °C in cuvettes of 1 cm optical path. Absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Cary 4 spectrophotometer (Varian) and a FluoroMax 3.0 (Jobin Yvon, Horiba) spectrofluorometer, respectively. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were performed with the time-correlated, single-photon counting technique using the excitation pulses at 315 nm provided by a pulse-picked frequency tripled Ti-sapphire laser (Tsunami, Spectra Physics) pumped by a Millennia X laser (Spectra Physics) as described elsewhere²⁰. The emission was collected through a polarizer set at the magic angle and an 8-nm band-pass monochromator (Jobin-Yvon H10) at 420 nm and 540 nm, respectively. The single-photon events were detected with a micro-channel plate photomultiplier (Hamamatsu) coupled to a pulse pre-amplifier HFAC (Becker-Hickl) and recorded on a SPC-130 board (Becker-Hickl). The instrumental response function was recorded using a polished aluminium reflector and its full width at half-maximum was ~ 40 ps. An integrated counts of 10^6 were collected for all of the lifetime measurements. For time-resolved anisotropy measurements, the fluorescence decay curves were recorded at vertical and horizontal positions of the polarizer and analyzed by the following equations :

$$I_{VV}(t) = I(t)[1 + 2r(t)]/3 \quad (4)$$

$$I_{VH}(t) = I(t)[1 - r(t)]/3 \quad (5)$$

$$r(t) = [I_{VV}(t) - G I_{VH}(t)]/[I_{VV}(t) + 2G I_{VH}(t)] \quad (6)$$

where I_{VV} and I_{VH} are the intensities collected at parallel and perpendicular emission polarizations, respectively, to the polarization axis of the excitation beam, and G is the geometry factor at the emission wavelength, determined in independent experiments, $I(t)$ and $r(t)$ are the time-dependent intensity (at magic angle) and anisotropy decay, respectively. The time-resolved intensity and anisotropy decays were analyzed together with the instrument response function using an iterative deconvolution method²¹ which enabled us to record the decay kinetics with a time constant as fast as ~ 10 ps with reasonable accuracy. The goodness of the fit was evaluated from the reduced χ^2 values, the plots of the residuals and the autocorrelation function^{20,21}. In all cases, the χ^2 values were close to 1, and the weighted residuals as well as the autocorrelation

of the residuals were distributed randomly around zero, indicating an optimal fit.

Results and discussion

(A) UV-Vis absorption :

The UV-Vis absorption of FHC were investigated systematically in non-ionic micelles to examine the influence of the micellar environment on the photophysics of the dye. Fig. 1 displays the UV-Vis absorption spectra of FHC in Triton X-100, Tween-20 and Brij-58 micelles as well as in water. The ground state absorption maximum

Fig. 1. Normalized absorption spectra of FHC in water and micelles : [FHC] = 7 μ M.

of FHC undergoes a red shift of \sim 10–12 nm in micelles (Table 1) compared to an aprotic solvent like acetonitrile, with an additional small shoulder around 322–324 nm. The red shift of the absorption maximum in non-ionic

micelles is similar to the moderate red shift observed earlier¹³ in alcohols when compared to polar aprotic solvents and may therefore be attributed to an intermolecular H-bonding interaction of the 4-carbonyl group of the FHC dye with water molecules of the micelle-water interface, which indicates to the dye's location in the palisade layer.

(B) Steady state emission spectroscopy :

FHC displays a dual fluorescence with two highly resolved emission bands (Fig. 2) in all of the three non-ionic micelles, while in water the long wavelength band is not well resolved and appears as a shoulder in the peak normalized steady-state emission spectrum. The demonstration of dual emission bands in micelles and water suggests the occurrence of an excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) reaction^{13,22}. The short-wavelength band corresponds to an emission of the excited normal (N*) form, while the long-wavelength band originates from the proton-transferred tautomer (T*, Scheme 2).

The excitation spectra monitored at the short (\sim 420 nm) and the long-wavelength (\sim 540 nm) emission bands in micelles are identical, and closely resemble the corresponding absorption spectrum (Fig. 3) demonstrating that the dual emission bands originate from the same ground-state precursor. Two spectral features of the steady state emission spectra of FHC in the non-ionic micelles, namely the (i) ratio of intensities of the N* and T* emission bands, (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) and (ii) positions of the N* and T* band maxima and their difference, ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) are noteworthy, when compared to water and a number of polar protic and aprotic solvents.

Table 1. Steady-state photophysical parameters of FHC in micelles and solvents

Micelle/Solvent	λ_{abs} (nm)	λ_{N^*} (nm)	λ_{T^*} (nm)	Φ	I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}	$\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$ (cm^{-1})	α	HLB
Triton X-100	360	418	535	0.066	0.21	5232		13.5
Tween-20**	358	420	535	0.090	0.33	5120		16.7
Brij-58**	358	416	535	0.076	0.26	5350		15.7
Water**	357	427	509	0.058	3.73	3770	1.01	
Ethanol	356	414	534	0.080	0.64	5428	0.36	
Methanol	356	421	530	0.080	1.71	4885	0.43	
Acetonitrile	348	409	533	0.060	0.10	5688	0.07	
Dimethylformamide	353	414	537	0.070	0.12	5533	-	

λ_{abs} : Absorption maximum; λ_{N^*} and λ_{T^*} : fluorescence maxima of the N* and T* forms, respectively; Φ , fluorescence quantum yield; I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} : intensity ratio of the dual emission maxima; α and HLB : Abraham's H-bond acidity⁴⁰ and hydrophile-lipophile balance of surfactants, respectively^{10,11}. $\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$: difference in emission maxima of the N* and T* bands, in cm^{-1} . **"Reprinted with permission from Langmuir, 2012, 28 (18), pp 7147–7159 by Das et al. Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society".

Fig. 2. Peak normalized emission spectra of FHC (7 μM) in micelles at 298 K; excitation wavelength is 330 nm; "Reprinted with permission from Langmuir, 2012, 28 (18), pp 7147–7159 by Das et al. Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society".

Fig. 3. Normalized absorption and excitation spectra in Triton X-100.

(1) Intensity ratio (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) of the N^* and T^* bands :

The ratio of intensities (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) of the short (N^*) and the long-wavelength (T^*) emission bands is larger in the non-ionic micelles than the aprotic solvents like acetonitrile or dimethylformamide and exhibits a variation with the hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) of the non-ionic surfactants (Table 1). The intensity of the N^* band was found to increase relative to the T^* band (Fig. 3) on an increase of the HLB of the non-ionic surfactants, in going along the sequence of Triton X-100 \rightarrow Brij-58 \rightarrow Tween-

20 followed by a gradual increase of the (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) value from 0.21 to 0.33 (Table 1).

Higher values of the intensity ratio (I_{N^*}/I_{T^*}) for the non-ionic micelles than acetonitrile may be attributed to a slower proton-transfer dynamics in the former compared to an unresolvably fast ESIPT reaction in the aprotic solvent¹³. Alternatively²³, this higher intensity ratio may be due to the formation of solvated structures with disrupted intramolecular H-bond unfavorable for an ESIPT reaction, because a strong FHC-water hydrogen bonding interaction with a concomitant disruption of the intramolecular H-bond is likely to be favored in strongly hydrated micelles with a consequent increase in intensity of the N^* emission band. However, this alternative model²³ requires a ground state heterogeneity (i.e. the presence of differently solvated dye molecules) which is absent in the non-ionic micelles due to (i) the lack of a significant difference between the excitation spectra, when monitored at the dual emission bands and (ii) its close analogy with the absorption spectra (Fig. 3). In consequence, the observation of a stronger N^* band in the neutral micelles may be attributed to the occurrence of a slower ESIPT dynamics, which is further verified from time-resolved fluorescence measurements.

(2) Position of the N^* and T^* band maxima and their difference ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) :

The N^* band undergoes an appreciable red shift of ~ 7 – 12 nm, while the T^* band is slightly blue shifted by ~ 2 nm in the non-ionic micelles (Table 1) when compared to the polar aprotic solvents. A further red and blue shift of the N^* and T^* bands, by ~ 9 – 11 nm and ~ 27 nm, respectively, were observed in water relative to these micelles. In consequence, the difference of the N^* and T^* emission maxima, ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) increases sequentially in the order : water < non-ionic micelles < aprotic solvents. The lower value of ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) in the non-ionic micelles, compared to acetonitrile or dimethylformamide may be attributed to intermolecular H-bonding interactions^{13,24} between FHC and water molecules in the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface. The oxygen atom of the 4-carbonyl group in FHC possesses an effective negative charge¹⁴ in the N^* state to facilitate an intermolecular H-bonding interaction, while in the T^* state this negative charge is compensated by the transferred proton, (Scheme 1) leading to a selective stabilization of the N^* state and destabilization of the T^* state by water molecules in the micelle-water interface.

A comparison of the ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) parameter in the non-ionic micelles to a number of polar protic solvents (Table 1) provides valuable insights on the micellar environment of the dye. For the non-ionic micelles, the difference in the band maxima ($\sim 5100\text{--}5300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is found to be close to that of a H-bond donating solvent like ethanol ($\sim 5400\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Moreover, several studies^{25–27} on the solubilization of fluorescence probes in micelles, revealed their preferential location in the Stern or palisade layer resembling closely the probe environment in short-chain alcohols^{25,26}. Thus, the close resemblance of the ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) parameter between the non-ionic micelles and ethanol indicates to the preferential location of FHC in the palisade layer of the non-ionic micelles. Furthermore, the ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) parameter in water is even smaller ($\sim 3800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) compared to these micelles, suggesting that a conducive environment for strong H-bonding interaction between FHC and water molecules is likely to be accompanied by a smaller ($\nu_{N^*} - \nu_{T^*}$) value and vice-versa. These observations led us to conjecture that FHC is likely located in the palisade layer of the non-ionic micelles, where the environment is less polar and less favorable for H-bonding interactions than bulk water. To monitor how the ESIPT dynamics of FHC is influenced by the H-bonding interactions in the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface, time-resolved fluorescence measurements were performed.

Time-resolved fluorescence spectroscopy :

(A) Time-resolved intensity decay :

In non-ionic micelles, time-resolved fluorescence decays (Figs. 4 and 5) at the N^* band is predominantly monoexponential comprising a fast component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) and a long-lived decay component ($\tau_2^{N^*}$) (Table 2) with very small amplitude. On the other hand, the fluorescence decays monitored at the T^* band are always characterized by a fast rise ($\tau_1^{T^*}$) and a slower decay component ($\tau_2^{T^*}$). The rise component ($\tau_1^{T^*}$) correlates well with the fast decay component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) (Table 2), demonstrating that the decay of the normal form (N^*) is coupled with the rise of the tautomer form (T^*) in the excited state and confirms the formation of the tautomeric form from the primarily excited normal form, through an ESIPT reaction ($N^* \rightarrow T^*$, Scheme 1). Furthermore, the long-lived decay components ($\tau_2^{N^*}$, $\tau_2^{T^*}$) may be ascribed to the lifetime of the primarily excited normal (N^*) and the proton-transferred tautomer (T^*) forms, respectively.

Fig. 4. Time-resolved decay of FHC in TX-100 micelles.

Fig. 5. Time-resolved decay in Tween-20 micelles.

Since the short-wavelength emission band ascribed to the excited normal (N^*) form of FHC is characterized by a very low quantum yield (Φ_{N^*}) ($\sim 1\text{--}2 \times 10^{-2}$) and a fast decay component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) ($\sim 30\text{--}66\text{ ps}$; Tables 2 and 3), it can be unambiguously conjectured that the time-resolved decay of the N^* form in non-ionic micelles is dominated by the rate constant, (k_{PT}) of the ESIPT reaction so that the fast decay component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) may be regarded as a measure of the time constant of the excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (τ^{PT}) reaction, $\tau_1^{N^*} \approx \tau^{PT}$ (Table 3) similar to our time-resolved data for FHC in polar solvents¹³. The long-lived decay component (τ_2) is systematically observed for the T^* band, but for the N^* band it is observed with a negligibly small amplitude (Table 2) suggesting an irreversible¹³ ESIPT for the FHC

Table 2. Time-resolved decay parameters of the dual emission bands of FHC in micelles

Micelle	$\tau_1^{N^*}$ (ns)	$a_1^{N^*}$	$\tau_2^{N^*}$ (ns)	$a_2^{N^*}$	$\chi_{N^*}^2$	$\tau_1^{T^*}$ (ns)	$a_1^{T^*}$	$\tau_2^{T^*}$ (ns)	$a_2^{T^*}$	$\chi_{T^*}^2$
Triton X-100	0.030	0.91	0.38	0.09	1.04	0.032	-0.49	1.45	0.51	1.11
Brij-58**	0.041	0.91	0.46	0.09	1.06	0.045	-0.50	1.43	0.50	0.97
Tween-20**	0.066	0.92	0.37	0.08	0.96	0.055	-0.49	1.57	0.51	1.21
Acetonitrile	<0.010	0.92	0.103	0.08	1.26	<0.010	-0.47	0.79	0.53	1.15
DMF	0.023	0.98	0.089	0.02	1.13	0.021	-0.48	0.89	0.52	1.20

τ_1 , τ_2 are the short-lived and long-lived decay times, respectively; a_1 , a_2 are the relative amplitudes; $\chi_{N^*}^2$ and $\chi_{T^*}^2$ are the reduced chi-square of fit to the time-resolved decays of the short and long wavelength emission bands, respectively. The error for all values of τ_1 , τ_2 is $\pm 10\%$ due to the precision of the measurements. Amplitudes were normalized according to $|a_1| + |a_2| = 1$. **"Reprinted with permission from *Langmuir*, 2012, 28 (18), pp. 7147–7159 by Das et al. Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society".

Table 3. Kinetic constants of ESIPT and radiative process in micelles

Micelle	Φ_{N^*}	$\tau_1^{N^*}(\tau_{PT})$ (ns)	$k_R^{N^*} \times 10^{-8}$ (s^{-1})	$k_{PT} \times 10^{-10}$ (s^{-1})	HLB
Triton X-100	0.011	0.030	3.66	3.33	13.5
Brij-58**	0.014	0.041	3.41	2.44	15.7
Tween-20**	0.020	0.066	3.03	1.52	16.7
Dimethylformamide	0.009	0.023	4.00	4.35	

Φ_{N^*} is the quantum yield of the N^* form; $\tau_1^{N^*}$ is the short-lived decay component of the N^* form; $k_R^{N^*}$, k_{PT} are respectively, the radiative rate constant of the N^* form and ESIPT rate constant. The error for all values of $k_R^{N^*}$ and k_{PT} is $\pm 10\%$ due to the precision of the measurements. HLB is hydrophile-lipophile balance number of a micelle¹⁰, **"Reprinted with permission from *Langmuir*, 2012, 28 (18), pp. 7147–7159 by Das et al. Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society".

dye in the non-ionic micelles. To evaluate quantitatively the effect of the hydrophile-lipophile balance of the non-ionic surfactants on ESIPT dynamics, we used the following model of irreversible ESIPT, where quantum yield of the N^* band, (Φ_{N^*}) is related to the short-lived decay component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) of the N^* form by the following relations.

$$\Phi_{N^*} = k_R^{N^*} \cdot \tau_1^{N^*} \quad (7)$$

$$(\tau_1^{N^*})^{-1} = k_R^{N^*} + k_{NR}^{N^*} + k_{PT} \quad (8)$$

where $k_R^{N^*}$, $k_{NR}^{N^*}$ are the radiative and nonradiative rate constants of the N^* form, respectively, and k_{PT} is the proton-transfer rate constant. An estimation of Φ_{N^*} from the steady state fluorescence spectra and $\tau_1^{N^*}$ from the time-resolved fluorescence measurements (Table 2) allow us to obtain the values of the radiative decay constant $k_R^{N^*}$ from eq. (7) for FHC in the micelles. Further, on the basis of a very low quantum yield of the N^* band and its associated fast decay component (Table 2), the ESIPT reaction may be quite reasonably assumed to be much faster than the radiative and nonradiative deactivation processes, so that $k_{PT} \gg k_R^{N^*} + k_{NR}^{N^*}$. Then eq. (8) may be simplified as

$$(\tau_1^{N^*})^{-1} = k_{PT} \quad (9)$$

The time-resolved decay of the N^* band is characterized by a fast component, $\tau_1^{N^*} \sim 30$ ps (Table 3) in the Triton X-100 micelles, implying an ESIPT reaction with a rate constant, $k_{PT} \sim 3.3 \times 10^{10} s^{-1}$. This short-lived decay component ($\tau_1^{N^*}$) increases moderately to ~ 41 ps in the Brij-58 micelles and becomes significantly longer ($\tau_1^{N^*} \sim 66$ ps) in the Tween-20 micelles with a $k_{PT} \sim 1.5 \times 10^{10} s^{-1}$. Thus, the time-resolved fluorescence measurements highlight a decrease in the ESIPT rate constant with an increase in the hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) of the non-ionic surfactants (Table 3). Moreover, the intramolecular proton-transfer dynamics is significantly slower in the non-ionic micelles compared to a polar aprotic solvent like dimethylformamide (Table 3), which is consistent with the variation of the I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} ratio (Table 1). These observations may be attributed to a difference in the extent of hydration of the surfactant headgroups in the non-ionic micelles, sensed by the FHC dye, because of its possible location in the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface. For a further clarification of the dye's location in the micelle-water interface, time-resolved anisotropy measurements were carried out.

(B) Time-resolved anisotropy decay :

The time-resolved anisotropy decays for the long-wavelength emission band were adequately described by a biexponential function, eq. (10) as evident from the satisfactory values of the reduced chi-square (χ^2) parameter (Table 4)

$$r(t) = r_0[\alpha_1 \exp(-t/\varphi_1) + \alpha_2 \exp(-t/\varphi_2)] \quad (10)$$

where r_0 is the initial anisotropy, α_i is the amplitude of the i -th rotational correlation time φ_i such that $\sum \alpha_i = 1$.

the equilibrium concentrations of the free dye to the micelle-bound dye (Table 4), estimated from the binding constants (K_d) of FHC with the micelles²⁸. This indicates that the anisotropy decays in micelles originate from rotational diffusion of the FHC dye bound to the micelles. So, the biexponential anisotropy decay could possibly be related to the FHC dye bound to two different sites of a micelle, namely the hydrophobic core, and the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface.

Table 4. Time-resolved anisotropy decay parameters of FHC in micelles

Micelle	τ_1 (ns)	α_1	τ_2 (ns)	α_2	χ^2	S	τ_w (ns)	$\alpha_1/\alpha_2 \times 10$	$[P]_f/[P]_b \times 10^3$
Triton X-100	0.610	0.35	4.55	0.65	1.11	0.81	0.71	7.24	2.25
Brij-58**	0.506	0.40	3.70	0.60	1.23	0.77	0.59	5.62	0.96
Tween-20**	0.476	0.42	2.77	0.58	1.22	0.76	0.58	7.24	1.50

τ_1 and τ_2 are the fast and slow rotational correlation times, respectively; α_1 , α_2 are the relative amplitudes; χ^2 is the reduced chi-square of fit parameter to the anisotropy decays; S and τ_w are the generalized order parameter and the time constant for wobbling motion respectively; $[P]_f$ and $[P]_b$ are respective concentrations of free and micelle-bound FHC, calculated at 7 μ M dye concentration. The error for all values of φ_1 , φ_2 is $\pm 10\%$ due to the precision of the measurements. **"Reprinted with permission from *Langmuir*, 2012, 28 (18), pp 7147-7159 by Das et al. Copyright 2012 American Chemical Society".

The biexponential anisotropy decays (Fig. 6) in the non-ionic micelles do not originate from the distribution of the dye molecule between the aqueous and the micellar

Fig. 6

phase, because the ratio of the amplitudes (α_1/α_2) of the fast (φ_1) and slow (φ_2) correlation times differs by two to three orders of magnitude from the ratio ($[P]_f/[P]_b$) of

However, this two-site model²⁹ would require a biexponential time-resolved fluorescence decay of the ESIPT tautomer (T^*) with two lifetime components, associated with the dye's location in two different sites of the micelle. But, in sharp contrast to this expectation, a monoexponential fluorescence decay of the ESIPT tautomer (T^*) of FHC with only one lifetime component, $\tau_2^{T^*}$ (Table 2) is observed. In addition, as FHC is poorly soluble in alkane-like solvents, but possesses a moderate to good solubility in water and protic solvents, and as it is highly polar because of its reasonably high ground and excited state dipole moments and charge distributions¹⁴, it must be located³⁰ in the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface, due to the higher polarity and water content of this region than the nonpolar hydrophobic core.

In consequence, the observed biexponential anisotropy decays may be attributed to two different kinds of motion of the FHC dye in micelles, according to the two-step and wobbling in a cone model³¹⁻³³. In this model, the dye molecule is proposed to undergo a lateral diffusion on the curved micelle surface and a fast wobbling motion in an imaginary cone coupled to the overall rotation of the micelle. The observed fast, (φ_1) and slow, (φ_2) rotational correlation times (Table 4) are related to the time

constants for lateral diffusion, (τ_L), wobbling motion, (τ_W) and the overall rotation of the micelle, (τ_M) by the following relations.

$$1/\tau_1 = 1/\tau_W + 1/\tau_L + 1/\tau_M \quad (11)$$

$$1/\tau_2 = 1/\tau_L + 1/\tau_M \quad (12)$$

This model⁴⁰⁻⁴², describes the decay of the time-resolved rotational anisotropy decay as

$$r(t) = r_0 [\beta \exp(-t/\phi_2) + (1 - \beta) \exp(-t/\phi_1)] \quad (13)$$

where, $\beta = S^2$. The generalized order parameter (S) is a measure of the spatial restriction of the dye motion within the micelle and satisfies the condition $0 \leq S^2 \leq 1$. If the motion is isotropic $S = 0$, and if it is completely hindered, $|S| = 1$. Additionally, the time constant for the wobbling motion (τ_W) of the dye may be regarded as a measure of the dynamics of the dye-perturbed local micelle structure²⁹, which depends on the nature of packing of the surfactant headgroups around the intercalated dye in micelles.

Probe location in micelles :

If the FHC molecules were located in the hydrophobic interior of the micelles, their wobbling motion would have been almost isotropic with a very low value of the order parameter, ($|S| \approx 0$), because the interior of the micelle is known to closely resemble a liquid hydrocarbon. In contrast, quite high values of the order parameter ($|S| \geq 0.77$, Table 4) were observed, which is consistent with the location of the FHC dye in the palisade layer (Scheme 1) of the nonionic micelles which corresponds to a region of high degree of order in the micelle-water interface as a consequence of the ordered packing of the surfactant headgroups. The much higher degree of order near the micelle-water interface, than that of the hydrophobic interior of a micelle was established earlier from NMR relaxation experiments^{34,35}.

Slower ESIPT dynamics in the palisade layer and its dependence on the hydrophile-lipophile balance of non-ionic surfactants :

The slower ESIPT dynamics of the FHC dye (Tables 2 and 3) in non-ionic micelles ($\tau^{PT} \sim 30-66$ ps) compared to an aprotic solvent like acetonitrile ($\tau^{PT} < 10$ ps), or dimethylformamide ($\tau^{PT} \sim 23$ ps) is consistent with its location in the palisade layer of the micelle-water interface. As the FHC dye is localized in the palisade

layer of the micelle-water interface, and since the palisade layer have water molecules associated with the non-ionic surfactant headgroups, the slower proton-transfer dynamics in the non-ionic micelles may quite reasonably be attributed to a weakening of the intramolecular H-bond between the 3-hydroxy and the 4-carbonyl group, as a consequence of the formation of an intermolecular H-bond (Scheme 3) between the water molecule and the 4-carbonyl group of FHC. Since the intramolecular H-bond is the pathway to the ESIPT process, its weakening due to a competitive intermolecular H-bonding interaction with water molecules in the palisade layer is likely to decrease the ESIPT rate of FHC in non-ionic micelles, similar to the earlier observations for 3-hydroxyflavone^{36,37}, FHC¹³ and 4-(dialkylamino)-3-hydroxyflavones in protic solvents³⁸.

Scheme 3. Mechanism of slow ESIPT in the micelle-water interface.

As the slower proton transfer dynamics in micelles was attributed to a weakening of the intramolecular H-bond between the 4-carbonyl and the 3-hydroxy moieties, as a consequence of the formation of an intermolecularly H-bonded complex (Scheme 3), the weakening of this intramolecular H-bond depends on the strength of the competitive intermolecular H-bonding interaction of the 4-carbonyl group of FHC with water molecules in the palisade layer, which in turn, depends on the extent of hydration of the polar headgroups in the palisade layer of different non-ionic micelles. As a consequence, stronger hydration of the non-ionic micelles should have led to the slower ESIPT dynamics and vice-versa. This expectation was indeed borne out nicely by the manifestation of a hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) sensitive ESIPT dynamics in non-ionic micelles.

The hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) of the non-ionic surfactants describes the relative ratio of hydro-

philic to hydrophobic regions^{10,11}, and higher HLB values correspond to the presence of higher hydrophilic portions relative to hydrophobic portions within a surfactant molecule and vice-versa. The palisade layer of the non-ionic micelles comprises poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) chains as the hydrophilic moiety. These PEO chains terminate into single or multiple -OH groups (Scheme 1), which along with the oxyethylene ether linkages bind³⁹ water molecules through intermolecular H-bonding interactions in the palisade layer of the non-ionic micelles. Thus, the palisade layer of the non-ionic Triton X-100 micelles is weakly hydrated because of the lower HLB (~13.5) of its surfactants (Table 3) compared to the palisade layer of the Brij-58 and Tween-20 micelles with higher HLB values of their surfactants (~15.7 and 16.7, respectively). So, the strength of the intermolecular H-bonding interaction of the 4-carbonyl group of FHC with water molecules, which competes with the intramolecular H-bond between the 3-hydroxy and 4-carbonyl moieties (Scheme 3) is weaker in the palisade layer of the Triton X-100 micelles than the Brij-58 or Tween-20 micelles. As a consequence, the intramolecular H-bond in FHC is likely to be less perturbed through hydration of the palisade layer in Triton X-100 micelles compared to the Brij-58 or Tween-20 micelles, and the ESIPT reaction is fastest with a kinetic constant of $3.3 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$. On the other hand, hydration of the palisade layer increases in going from Triton X-100 to Brij-58 micelles, because of the higher HLB of the corresponding Brij-58 surfactants (~15.7) which causes a greater extent of perturbation of the intramolecular H-bond in FHC leading to a slower ESIPT dynamics ($k_{\text{PT}} \sim 2.44 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$, Table 3) in the palisade layer of the Brij-58 micelles than the Triton X-100 micelles. The hydration of the palisade layer increases further in going from the Brij-58 micelles (HLB ~15.7) to Tween-20 micelles (HLB ~16.7), and the ESIPT reaction becomes slowest in the Tween-20 micelles because of a strong perturbation of the intramolecular H-bond in FHC, which originates due to the stronger hydration of the palisade layer of Tween-20 micelles than the Brij-58 or Triton X-100 micelles.

Moreover, the non-ionic poly(ethylene oxide) surfactants appear to be more tightly packed in the Triton X-100 micelles than in the Brij-58 or Tween-20 micelles, as evident from the higher values of the order parameter, S

and the time constant for wobbling motion, τ_{W} in Triton X-100 (Table 4), which causes a lesser extent of water penetration in the palisade layer of the Triton X-100 micelles than the Brij-58 or Tween-20 micelles. Thus, apart from the HLB parameter of the non-ionic surfactants, rigidity of the micelle environment or the local micelle structure may also contribute to the variation in the extent of hydration of the non-ionic micelles, and hence to a variation in the ESIPT dynamics in different types of non-ionic micelles.

Conclusions :

The ESIPT dynamics of the FHC dye is sensitive to the hydration of the non-ionic micelles, with an inverse correlation of its kinetic constant (k_{PT}) to the hydrophile-lipophile balance (HLB) of the non-ionic surfactants. Whereas the ESIPT is fastest in the palisade layer of the poorly hydrated Triton X-100 micelles, it is slower in the palisade layer for the moderately hydrated Brij-58 micelles, and slowest in the palisade layer of the strongly hydrated Tween-20 micelles. The gradual decrease of the ESIPT rate constant in going along the sequence of Triton X-100 → Brij-58 → Tween-20 micelles is attributed to the gradual increase of the HLB parameter of the non-ionic surfactants, implying an increase of the hydrophilicity and hence in the extent of hydration in going from the palisade layer of the Triton X-100 micelles to the Tween-20 micelles.

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References

1. S. Mahiuddin, O. Zech, S. Raith, D. Touraud and W. Kunz, *Langmuir.*, 2009, **25**, 12516.
2. J. B. Engberts and J. Kevelam, *Curr. Opi. Colloid. Interface. Sci.*, 1996, **1**, 779.
3. D. V. Tulumello and C. M. Deber, *Biochemistry*, 2009, **48**, 12096.
4. (a) R. G. Weiss, V. Ramamurthy and G. S. Hammond, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 530; (b) K. Kalyansundaram, "Photochemistry in Microheterogeneous Systems", Academic Press, New York, 1991.
5. J. C. Lima, C. Vautier-Giongo, A. Lopes, E. C. Melo, F. H. Quina and A. L. Macüanita, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2002, **106**, 5851.

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6. L. Giestas, C. Yihwa, J. C. Lima, C. V. Giongo, A. Lopes, A. L. Macanita and F. H. Quina, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2003, **107**, 3263.
7. K. M. Solnetsev, Y. V. Ilichev, A. B. Demyaskevich and M. G. Kuzmin, *J Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1994, **78**, 39.
8. R. Adhikary, P. J. Carlson, T. W. Kee and J. W. Petrich, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 2997.
9. (a) P. Mukherjee and J. R. Cardinal, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 1620; (b) K. N. Ganesh, P. Mitra and D. Balasubramanium, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 4291.
10. The anonymous reviewer is thanked, for kindly providing the modified definition of the HLB parameter.
11. S. K. Hait and S. P. Moulik, *J. Surfactants Detergents*, 2001, **4**, 303.
12. S. K. Mehta, G. Kaur and K. K. Bhasin, *AAPS Pharm. Sci. Tech.*, 2010, **11**, 143.
13. R. Das, A. S. Klymchenko, G. Duportail and Y. Mely, *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.*, 2009, **8**, 1583.
14. C. A. Kenfack, A. S. Klymchenko, G. Duportail, A. Burger and Y. Mely, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, **14**, 8910.
15. V. V. Shvadchak, A. S. Klymchenko, H.d. Rocquigny and Y. Mely, *Nucleic. Acids Res.*, 2009, **37**, 1.
16. M. Almgren, F. Grieser and J. K. Thomas, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 279.
17. S. M. Ormson, R. G. Brown, F. Vollmer and W. Rettig, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.*, (A) 1994, **81**, 65.
18. D. A. Yushchenko, V. V. Shvadchak, M. D. Bilokin, A. S. Klymchenko, G. Duportail, Y. Mely and V. Pivovarenko, *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.*, 2006, **5**, 1038.
19. D. B. Siano and D. E. Metzler, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, **51**, 1856.
20. J. Godet, N. Ramalanjaona, K. K. Sharma, L. Richert, H.d. Rocquigny, J. L. Darlix, G. Duportail and Y. Mely, *Nucleic. Acids Res.*, 2011, **39**, 6633.
21. T. Goel, T. Mukherjee, B. J. Rao and G. Krishnamoorthy, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2010, **114**, 8986.
22. A. S. Klymchenko and A. P. Demchenko, *New. J. Chem.*, 2004, **28**, 687.
23. D. McMorrow and M. Kasha, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 2235.
24. A. S. Klymchenko and A. P. Demchenko, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2003, **5**, 461.
25. R. Zana, "Surfactant Solutions : New Methods of Investigation", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1987.
26. G. F. Sanchez and C. C. Ruiz, *J. Lumin.*, 1996, **69**, 179.
27. J. Hadjianestis and J. Nikokavouras, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1993, **69**, 337.
28. R. Das, (manuscript in preparation).
29. M. E. L. McBain, "Solubilization and Related Phenomena", Academic Press Inc., New York, 1955.
30. G. Lipari and A. Szabo, *Biophys. J.*, 1980, **30**, 489.
31. K. Kinoshita, S. Kawato and A. Ikegami, *Biophys. J.*, 1977, **20**, 289.
32. A. Szabo, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **81**, 150.
33. N. C. Maiti, M. M. G. Krishna, P. J. Britto and N. Periasamy, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1997, **101**, 11051.
34. H. Walderhaug, O. Smerman and P. Stilbs, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 1655.
35. H. Nery, O. Soderman, D. Canet, H. Walderhaug and B. Lindman, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 5802.
36. P. F. Barbara and A. G. Strandjord, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 2355.
37. S. Ameer-Beg, S. Ormson, R. G. Brown, P. Matousek, M. Towrie, P. Foggi and F. V. Neuwahl, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 3709.
38. V. Shynkar, A. S. Klymchenko, E. Péemont, A. P. Demchenko and Y. Mely, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2004, **108**, 8151.
39. R. Kjellander and E. Florin, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday. Trans. 1*, 1981, **77**, 2053.
40. M. J. Kamlet, J. L. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877.

